

Translate the interview transcript from Russian to English. Requirements:

- Preserve meaning and factual content exactly.
- Do not add, remove, or infer information.
- Translate only; do not summarize, reinterpret, or improve the content. Preserve original structure, formatting, timestamps, punctuation, and speaker order.
- Keep speaker labels exactly as in the original. Do not rename or normalize names.
- Do not correct grammar, style, or improve clarity. Preserve spoken language, hesitations, and informal speech.
- If some words or phrases are already in English, keep them as-is unless context requires translation.
- Maintain consistent translation of repeated terms across all chunks.

I will send the transcript in multiple chunks. Treat each chunk independently and do not merge information across chunks. Output only the English translation. No explanations, comments, or additional text. Insert a blank line between each speaker turn.